

Eliminating Magnetic Components in a 48-to-12V Switched Tank Converter for Data Center Applications

Sotirios Filippas ¹, Georgios Kampitsis ¹

¹ University of Patras, Greece

Corresponding author: Sotirios Filippas, filippas.s@ac.upatras.gr
 Speaker: Sotirios Filippas, filippas.s@ac.upatras.gr

Abstract

For 48-to-Point-of-Load conversion, switched-tank converters (STCs) are adopted for their high efficiency and superior energy density compared to magnetic-based designs. However, despite relying only on capacitors for energy conversion, STCs still require magnetic elements for capacitors' soft charging and transistors' soft switching. These inductors occupy significant volume and limit overall power density and output current. In this work, a high-power 48-to-12 V STC is designed and experimentally validated up to 600 W, with no magnetic components, by utilizing only the stray inductance of the PCB to eliminate switching losses, while suppressing charge redistribution losses. The prototype achieved a power density of 1413 W/inch³, and a peak efficiency of 97.4 %.

1 Introduction

The transition from 12 V to 48 V in the automotive market [1] and the rapid growth of data centers has driven the demand for efficient and power-dense 48-to-point-of-load (PoL) converters [2]. Among the different topologies, switched capacitor (SC) converters have emerged as a promising solution, benefiting from the much higher energy density of capacitors compared to inductors and transformers. Moreover, additional advantages arise with SC converters in terms of simplicity and compactness by the fact that electrical isolation is not required in these applications. A well-known limitation of SC

converters is the power losses that occur due to the charge redistribution between switching cycles [3]. To overcome slow switching limit, inductors are often inserted into the charge redistribution paths, effectively limiting inrush currents and eliminating the mentioned losses [4]. These variations of SC converters, called Resonant SC converters (RSCC) or Switched Tank Converters (STCs), have demonstrated impressive performance, achieving power densities among the highest reported, with peak efficiencies often exceeding 96% [5]-[7]. Nevertheless, the necessary inductive components still occupy up to 12-15% of the total converter volume [5], [6]. Finally, the saturation current of inductors limits the output current, and in turn limits the output

Fig. 1: The 4-to-1 Switched Capacitor Converter, consisting of two 2-to-1 stages.

power.

In this work, the 48-to-12V Cascaded Resonant Converter concept first introduced in [5] is revisited, providing a way to eliminate discrete magnetic components, while attaining high efficiency and high-power density. The SC converter is presented in Fig. 1. It consists of 2 Cascaded 2-to-1 SC converters, while the 2nd stage consists of two parallel phases to carry higher current.

2 Converter Operation Principles

2.1 Analysis of a single stage

A single stage of the converter is shown in Fig. 2, and it is analyzed to calculate the resonant frequency (RF). Transistors switch complementary with a 50 % duty cycle based on their indicated color, to charge and discharge the flying capacitor C_1 , providing the 2:1 conversion. Stray inductances L_1 - L_6 are also included, and input and output capacitors are sufficiently large, so the RF is independent of their value. Thus, two resonant frequencies are formed given by Equation (1):

$$f_{r1} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{L_{pi1}C_1}}, \quad (1)$$

$$f_{r2} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{L_{pi2}C_1}}$$

where i is the stage and L_{pi1} and L_{pi2} are given by Equation (2):

$$L_{pi1} = L_1 + L_2 + L_3 + L_4, \quad (2)$$

$$L_{pi2} = L_2 + L_4 + L_5 + L_6$$

So, in every phase of operation series L-C sub-circuits are being formed as shown in Fig. 3(a), so the current through the capacitor will be sinusoidal, instead of impulsive. With a 50% duty cycle, if the

Fig. 2: A single stage of the converter, including parasitic inductances.

Fig. 3: (a) Two phases of operation and 2 formed resonant frequencies and (b) Currents through the flying capacitor and output node (through L_4).

inductances L_{pi1} and L_{pi2} are equal and the switching frequency matches the RF, the stage achieves complete Zero Current Switching (ZCS), eliminating switching losses. In practice, there is a slight mismatch between them, but they are very close. In Fig. 3(b), currents through the flying capacitor C_1 and through the output node (through L_4) are shown. Of course, in other implementations found in [5]-[6], you can choose the RF to be the same in all stages, but here it is highly dependent on the PCB layout and thus differ from stage to stage. As described in the next section this is not a problem.

2.2 Analysis, Simulation and Design Guidelines of the magnetic-less 48-to-12 V converter

2.2.1 Analysis and Simulations

As mentioned, two 2-to-1 switched-capacitor (SC) converters are cascaded to achieve the 4-to-1 conversion. The interleaved phases operate with an

180° difference, to minimize C_{MID} , as described in [8]. Due to the high intermediate capacitance and the high switching frequency (300 kHz - 500 kHz), the two stages are decoupled effectively, allowing them to operate at different switching frequencies. Thus, mismatches between the RF of the first and second stages are acceptable, but mismatches between the interleaved phases are not, since they operate at the same switching frequency. The STC is shown again in Fig. 4 with the stray inductances, and it is thoroughly simulated in LTspice for the case where the RFs between the two stages differ. We consider:

$$L_{pi1} = L_{pi2} = L_{pi} \quad (3)$$

$$L_{pj2j} = L_{pj3j} \quad (4)$$

where $i = 1, 2$ refers to the stage and $j = 1, \dots, 6$ refers to the inductances L_j in Fig. 2. We also consider the interleaved phases to be identical. Table 1 presents the simulation parameters, where the inductances between the stages, and thus the RFs, are different.

As seen in Fig. 5, soft switching for all transistors is achievable, even though the inductances vary. It is noted that this operation is only achievable if the two stages are decoupled, as indicated earlier.

2.2.2 Design Guidelines

There are some key considerations to be addressed during the design. Firstly, the PCB layout of Phases A and B in every stage, as indicated in Fig. 3(a), must be as symmetrical as possible, so that $L_{pi1} = L_{pi2}$. Otherwise, it will result in hard switching of the devices and thus lower efficiency. Secondly, the RF of the parallel phases must be the same.

Fig. 4: The 48-to-12V Magnetic-less STC with the stray inductances.

L_{p1}	8 nH
L_{p2}, L_{p3}	12 nH
C_1, C_2, C_3	15 μ F
F_{sw} (First stage)	459 kHz
F_{sw} (Second stage)	375 kHz
Output Current	30 A

Tab. 1: Simulation Parameters

Fig. 5: Current waveforms through the flying capacitors C_1 (top - 1st stage), C_2 and C_3 (bottom - 2nd stage).

Even if the stray inductances differ, there is an extra degree of freedom provided by the capacitances. Capacitors C_1 or C_2 can be adjusted to meet the desired resonant frequency, given by Eq. (1). Lastly, the design guidelines mentioned in [8] are also applicable here. There are no inductors in this implementation; thus, inductor saturation current and DC resistance, as mentioned in [5]–[6], do not limit the efficiency or the output current.

The RF can be calculated experimentally from the output current of each stage, since it is not known initially. Taking, for example, the circuit in Fig. 2, that has a RF of 375 kHz and an effective RF of 361 kHz, when dead time is taken into consideration, which is approximately 55 ns in this simulation. Dead time affects resonant operation, as the reduced conduction time prevents the current from reaching zero. This is resolved by operating at a lower switching frequency. Information about the effective RF can be extracted from the transistors' current during the switching phases.

Considering the transistors' on-resistances negligible, table 2 presents the three possible current conditions based on the switching frequency. Output currents for three different switching frequencies are shown in Fig. 6, where the current at the switching instant (I_{OFF}) is also indicated.

Condition 1	$f_{sw} > f_{res,eff}$	$I_{OFF} > 0$
Condition 2	$f_{sw} < f_{res,eff}$	$I_{OFF} < 0$
Condition 3	$f_{sw} = f_{res,eff}$	$I_{OFF} = 0$ (ZCS)

Tab. 2: Different Conditions regarding the switching frequency

Fig. 6: Current waveforms through the output node of a single stage of the converter for different switching frequencies. The effective RF equals 361 kHz.

Thus, the RF and the parasitic inductance are given by Eq. (5) and Eq. (6):

$$f_{r,ik} = \frac{\pi \mp \arcsin\left(\frac{|I_{off}|}{I_{max}}\right)}{2\pi t_{on}} \quad (5)$$

$$L_{pik} = \frac{1}{4\pi^2 f_{r,ik}^2 C_i} \quad (6)$$

where $k = 1, 2$ refers to the two phases of operation mentioned in Fig. 3(a). In Eq. (5) “-” and “+” are for the Conditions 1 and 2 respectively (table 2). Thus, the switching frequency is chosen as close to the estimated RF as possible.

3 Experimental Results

3.1 Hardware Prototype

To validate the concept, a 600 W RSCC was designed and experimentally tested for a current up to 53 A. The prototype is shown in Fig. 7.

An inexpensive 4-layer PCB (2 oz. external layers / 1oz. internal layers) is used. The top side consists of the power MOSFETs, flying and decoupling capacitors, while on the bottom side there is mainly gate driving circuitry with some more decoupling capacitors. The solid core cables appearing in the back are used to measure the current at the output nodes. All the gate drivers are supplied via the cascaded bootstrap method, as mentioned in [8],

Fig. 7: (a) Top side and (b) bottom side photographs of the experimental prototype of the Magnetic-less STC with dimensions $28.9 \times 41.5 \times 5.8$ mm³.

eliminating the need for bulky, isolated DC/DC converters. The most critical components of the design are listed in table 3.

Flying Capacitors C_1 and C_2 are equal to 14 μ F, after DC derating, while C_3 is equal to 19.6 μ F, so the paralleled phases have the same RF, as mentioned in Section 2.2.2.

3.2 Experimental Validation

To test the designed prototype, ITECH's DC Electronic load (IT8012-500-80) was used, as well as ITECH's bidirectional power supply (IT6018C-1500-40). DC output current is measured via PICO TA189, while the switching output currents in every stage were measured via a Rogowski-coil current probe.

Fig. 8 shows the experimental setup. Only fan cooling was enough for a current up to 25 A, while a heatsink attached to custom aluminum block was essential for higher power. Currents through the output nodes at full load are shown in Fig. 9. As seen, all transistors in the second stage are soft switched (ZCS) and there is an acceptable match-

Fig. 8: Experimental Setup.

Component	Part Number	Comments
1 st stage MOSFETs	IQE013N04LM6SC	40 V / 1.35 mΩ
2 nd stage MOSFETs	IQE006NE2LM5SC	25 V / 0.58 mΩ
Flying Capacitor C_1	CGA5L3X7R1H155K160AB	14×1.5 μF, 50 V, 1206, X7R
Flying Capacitor C_2	CGA5L3X7R1V155K160AB	10×1.5 μF, 35 V, 1206, X7R
Flying Capacitor C_3	CGA5L3X7R1V155K160AB	14×1.5 μF, 35 V, 1206, X7R
Decoupling Capacitors C_{MID}	CGA4J1X7R1H475K125AC	30×4.7 μF, 50 V, 0805, X7R
Decoupling Capacitors C_{OUT}	GRM21BC71E106KE01L	28×10 μF, 25 V, 0805
Bootstrap Diodes	BAS 52-02V H6327	45 V, Fast Schottky
Gate Drivers	LTC4440-5	High-side, 60 V

Tab. 3: Main components of the Magnetic-less STC

Fig. 9: Currents through the output nodes at 600 W. The first stage (top) operates at a switching frequency of 459 kHz, while the second stage (bottom) operates at a switching frequency of 316 kHz.

ing of the inductances L_{p21} and L_{p22} , as well as L_{p31} and L_{p32} . Furthermore, as indicated earlier, by choosing different C_2 and C_3 , the RFs between the interleaved stages are sufficiently matched.

On the other hand, this is not the case with the first stage's inductances L_{p11} and L_{p12} . They differ significantly, so there are switching losses, but charge redistribution losses are still suppressed. The first stage operates at 459 kHz, and the second stage operates at 316 kHz.

Nevertheless, efficiency, as presented in Fig. 10, remains high at all loads, because conduction losses dominate, as described in [5].

Efficiency peaked at 97.4 % for an output current of 20 A, reaching 94.61 % at full load. From Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) we can calculate the RF and stray inductances. Results are presented in table 4. L_{p11} appears to be twice as big as L_{p12} . Transient response of the converter is also tested. The output

Fig. 10: Power Converter's efficiency for an output power up to 600 W.

current changes rapidly from 10 A to 20 A, falling again to 15 A, after a while. The output voltage shows little to no fluctuation, as shown in Fig. 11. Output voltage versus load current is shown in Fig. 12. At full load, it drops by about 0.63 V, which translates into an equivalent output resistance of 11.8 mΩ.

The prototype achieved a power density of 1413

Fig. 11: Output Voltage (orange) response during load change conditions (blue).

	Stray Inductances (nH)	f_r (kHz)	f_{sw} (kHz)
L_{p11}	9.2	444.07	459
L_{p12}	5.3	582.44	
L_{p21}	13.6	364.74	316
L_{p22}	13.5	366.46	
L_{p31}	9.9	360.51	
L_{p32}	9.8	363.91	

Tab. 4: Calculated stray inductances based on the cutoff current during the switching phases.

Fig. 12: Output Voltage versus output current, up to a load current of 53 A.

W/inch³ or 87 kW/L. It is estimated that by redesigning the converter so that the solid core wires in Fig. 7 are removed and the decoupling capacitors are placed closer to the transistors, the power density can be further improved, to approximately 130 kW/L or 2130 W/inch³. The converter can also be used for automotive applications, due to its high efficiency and compact volume, while its switching frequency remains below the band of 500 kHz – 1.8 MHz.

4 Conclusion

In this work, a method was presented to eliminate inductors from STCs while highlighting their benefits. The proposed method can be applied to most existing STC topologies and is expected to significantly increase their power density for two main reasons: 1) further reduction of converter volume due to the removal of magnetics and 2) enabling operation at higher power, since inductor saturation current is no longer a limitation. The concept was experimentally validated in a 48-to-12 V Cascaded

Resonant Switched Capacitor Converter and successfully tested up to 600 W or up to 53 A output current, achieving a high-power density of 87 kW/L.

Acknowledgements

Funded by the European Union (ERC grant: ENRICH, Grant Agreement 101115709, DOI 10.3030/101115709). Views and opinions expressed are however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- [1] M. Eaker, *48 V Automotive Systems: Why Now?*, Texas Instruments, White Paper, Feb. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ti.com/lit/wp/slyy243/slyy243.pdf>
- [2] Infineon Technologies, *48 V Intermediate Bus Converter (IBC) in Data Centers – Power Distribution for AI and High Power Applications*, Infineon White Paper, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.infineon.com/cms/en/applications/communication/48v-power-distribution/>
- [3] M. D. Seeman and S. R. Sanders, “Analysis and Optimization of Switched-Capacitor DC–DC Converters,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 841–851, Mar. 2008, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2007.915182.
- [4] S. Jiang, S. Saggini, C. Nan, X. Li, C. Chung, and M. Yazdani, “Switched Tank Converters,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 5048–5062, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2018.2868447.
- [5] T. Ge, Z. Ye, R. A. Abramson, and R. C. N. Pilawa Podgurski, “A 48 to 12 V Cascaded Resonant Switched-Capacitor Converter Achieving 4068 W/in³ Power Density and 99.0% Peak Efficiency,” in *Proc. IEEE Appl. Power Electron. Conf. Expo. (APEC)*, Phoenix, AZ, USA, 2021, pp. 1335–1342, doi: 10.1109/APEC42165.2021.9487264.
- [6] T. Ge, Z. Ye, and R. C. N. Pilawa Podgurski, “A 48 to 12 V Cascaded Multi Resonant Switched-Capacitor Converter With 4700 W/in³ Power Density and 98.9% Efficiency,” in *Proc. IEEE En-*

ergy Conversion Congr. Expo. (ECCE), Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2021, pp. 1959–1965, doi: 10.1109/ECCE47101.2021.9595943.

- [7] C. Rainer, R. Rizzolatti, and D. Varajao, “High-Density Cascaded ZVS Switched Capacitor Converter for 48 V Data-Center Application,” in *PCIM Europe Digital Days*, Germany, 2020, pp. 1–8.
- [8] Z. Ye, Y. Lei, and R. C. N. Pilawa Podgurski, “The Cascaded Resonant Converter: A Hybrid Switched-Capacitor Topology With High Power Density and Efficiency,” *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 4946–4958, May 2020, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2019.2947218.